

RESEARCH PAPER

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Birds of mainit hot spring protected landscape, Nabunturan, compostela valley, Province Mindanao island, Philippines

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Article published on August 31, 2016

Key words: Birds, Endemic, Mainit hot spring, Philippines

Abstract

The present paper is part of the rapid biodiversity assessment in Mainit Hot Spring Protected Landscape (MHSPL), Nabunturan, Compostela Valley Province Philippines within the months of December 2012 and February 2013. Transect walk survey or visual encounter, mist netting, and live trapping methods were employed to 5 sampling sites namely, Sitio New Bohol (SNB), Sitio Saraban (SS), Sitio Pagtulian (SP), and Sitio Tindalo (ST). Total of (24) birds from 18 families are documented. More than half (13 of 24) are resident or 54%, 8 Philippine endemic (found throughout Philippines) 33%, 2 migrant 9%, and 1 species or 4% found only Mindanao Island or Mindanao endemic. Despite rampant mining and other socio-economic activities inside the MHSPL, there is still surviving species of aves in its remaining forests. Therefore, an urgent forest protection should be implemented especially in Sitio New Bohol and Sitio Tindalo where majority of endemic species are found.

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Introduction

The Philippines is very rich with different kinds of natural resources and its flora and fauna species are very diverse and unique. In fact it is one of the 17 mega-diverse countries in the world with very high endemism and species richness per unit area in the world in terms of numbers and percentage (Heaney *et al.*, 1998). But as the proportion of the forest decreases in the country, it greatly affects the survival and existence of species living in our Philippine forest. We believed that many of Philippine species cannot survive due to extensive socio-economic human activities in the forest. The loss of large numbers of wildlife simply indicates that the remaining faunal species will become endangered, and may lead to extinction if not well protected and conserved.

Mainit Hot Spring Protected Landscape is found at the northeastern region of the Philippine archipelago [N 7°30'00"; E 125°59'00"] located within the Municipality of Nabunturan, Province of Compostela Valley (Fig. 1). The whole range of MHSPL covers about 1,775 hectares including both the buffer and core zones. This area especially in the buffer zone is mostly planted with coconuts and other fruit-bearing trees. There are still remaining fragmented forest covers in remote areas such in Sitio Tindalo and Sitio New Bohol.

Since its declaration as Protected Area (PA) in the 1950s, there is no available taxonomic study of birds made in Mainit Hot Spring Protected Landscape. Faunal identification is necessary and important because it provides vital information and description of species and can be used by the policy makers in creating policies leading to the protection and preservation of MHSPL (Pettersson, 2006). Hence, this study was conducted to record and identify the various inhabiting avifaunal species in MHSPL.

Material and methods

This study was conducted at MHSPL, Nabunturan, Compostela Valley Province from December 2011 to March 2012. Five (5) sampling sites were identified: Sitio New Bohol, Sitio Saraban, SitioPagtulian, and Tindalo (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Map of the Philippines (A), Map of Mindanao (B) Map of Compostela Valley Province showing the location of Nabunturan (C) Map of the study area-MHSPL

Sampling

The sampling was done on December 2011 up to December 2012 at 4 sites in MHSPL: Sitio New Bohol, Sitio Saraban, Sitio Pagtulian, and Sitio Tindalo.

Design

Transect walk following a two-kilometer transect line was established with 20 interval points at 100 meters. Opportunistic sampling and visual encounter (Relox *et al.*, 2011) was also used and bio-acoustics were employed (Derlindati and Caziani, 2005) to increase the chance of sightings.

Methods

The mist nets were placed at 10 meters intervals in each sites and in accordance to their assumed flight paths such as clearing, along ridges or along river banks (Heaney *et al.*, 1998) and strategically established along the forest edge, flyways, foraging areas and forest interior (Relox *et al.*, 2011).

The nets were left open after establishing them checked every 30 minutes. All birds captured were retrieved from the mist nets for recording of their morph metrics and identification purposes.

Morph metrics in birds such as bill length (Bl), tarsus length (Tl), wingspan (W) and total length (TL) were measured using a caliper. Gender of each species was also noted. Morphological characteristics of each bird species were determined and compared to the book of Kennedy *et al.* (2000) and Heaney *et al.* (2010). Statistical analysis:

Result and discussion

The recent survey revealed Twenty four (24) birds from 18 families are documented comprising of 8 Philippine endemic, 1 Mindanao endemic, 2 Migrant, and 13 residents from 4 sites surveyed: Sitio New Bohol, Sitio Saraban, Sitio Pagtulian, and Sitio Tindalo. Table 1 shows all bird species documented in MHSPL.

Table 1. List of birds in MHSPL.

Family	Species	Local Name/ English Name	Endemism	Geographic distribution
Accipitridae	<i>Accipiter virgatus</i>	Sakbit	Least Concern	Phil. Endemi
Alcedinidae	<i>Alcedoargentata</i>	Silvery Kingfisher; Kibid	Rare and Vulnerable	Phil. Endemi
Apodidae	<i>Collocalia troglodytes</i>	Pygmy Swiftlet	Least Concern	Phil. Endemi
Columbidae	<i>Phapitreron leucotis</i>	White-eared brown dove; Alimocon (Vis)	Least Concern	Phil. Endemi
	<i>Chalcophalps indica</i>	Common emerald dove; Manatad (Vis)	Least Concern	Residen
Corvidae	<i>Corvus macrorhynchos</i>	Uwak; Large Billed crow	Least Concern	Residen
Cuculidae	<i>Centropus bengalensis</i>	Lesser Coucal; Kokok	Least Concern	Residen
	<i>Centropus viridis</i>	Philippine Coucal; Kokok	Least Concern	Phil. Endemi
Dicaeidae	<i>Dicaeum trigonostigma</i>	Orange Bellied Flowerpecker; Tikbay	Least Concern	Residen
	<i>Dicaeum australe</i>	Red-keeled flowerpecker; Panagoto (Vis)	Least Concern	Phil. Endemi
Estrildidae	<i>Lonchura leucogastra</i>	White Bellied Munia; Maya	Least Concern	Residen
	<i>Lonchura malacca</i>	Chestnut Munia	Least Concern	Residen
Hemiprocnidae	<i>Hemiprocne comata</i>	Whiskered treeswift; Sayaw	Least Concern	Residen
Hirundinidae	<i>Hirundo tahitica</i>	Pacific swallow; Balinsasayao (Vis)	Least Concern	Residen
Laniidae	<i>Lanius cristatu</i>	Brown shrike; Tibalas (Vis)	Least Concern	Migran
Meropidae	<i>Merops viridis</i>	Blue-throated Bee Eater; Purok-purok(Vis)	Least Concern	Residen
Motacillidae	<i>Motacilla flava</i>	Yellow wagtail	Least Concern	Migran
Nectariniidae	<i>Nectarinia jugularis</i>	Olive backed sunbird; Tamsi	Least Concern	Residen
	<i>Nectarinia sperata</i>	Purple throated sunbird; Tamsi	Least Concern	Residen
Psittacidae	<i>Bolbo psittacus lunulatus</i>	Guaiabero; Batotok (Pil)	Least Concern	Phil. Endemic
Pycnonotidae	<i>Pycnonotus goiavier</i>	Yellow Vented Bulbul; Pirok-pirok	Least Concern	Residen
Strigidae	<i>Otus mirus</i>	Mindanao Scops Owl	Near threatened	Mindanao Endemi
	<i>Aplonis minor</i>	Short Tailed Glossy Starling; Galansiang (Vis)	Least concern	Philippin Endemi
Sturnidae	<i>Aplonis panayensis</i>	Asian Glossy Starling; Galansiang (Vis)	Least concern	Residen

The recent survey revealed more than half (13 of 24) are resident or 54%, 8 Philippine endemic (found throughout Philippines) 33%, 2 migrant 9%, and 1 species or 4% found only Mindanao Island or Mindanao endemic (Fig. 2).

This data is relatively lower compared to avifaunal species documented by Relox *et al.* 2011 in Mt. Hamiguitan Range Wildlife Sanctuary in Davao Oriental with 20 Philippine endemic and 10 Mindanao endemic species.

Fig. 2. Avifaunal composition of MHSPL.

Perhaps the primary reason of minimal bird species in MHSPL is the rampant clearing of forests or timber harvesting, extensive mining where mostly used explosives that greatly disturbed bird species and perhaps causes imminent migration, and conversion of forests into agricultural purposes. Hence “kaingin” or burning of forests is very visible to almost all areas of MHSPL.

Reflected also in the data that mostly small species of resident birds dominated the open areas of MHSPL such as *Hirundo tahitica* (Balinsasayaw), *Aplonis panayensis* (Galansiang), *Lonchura leucogastra* (Maya) and *Nectarinia* species (Sun birds). Relatively large and Philippine endemic species such as *Otus mirus* (Mindanao Scops Owl) and *Centropus viridis* (Kokok) are seldom seen in the area. This also conform to the studies of Cooke (1980); Humphrey *et al.* (1987), and Holmes *et al.* (1993) that generally, bird species vary in tolerance levels where large species seem less tolerant of human disturbance than small ones.

Table 2. List of species captured/seen in sampling sites.

Family	Species	GD	Area captured or seen			
			SNB	SS	SP	ST
Accipitridae	<i>Accipiter virgatus</i>	PE	X			
Alcedinidae	<i>Alcedo argentata</i>	PE				X
Apodidae	<i>Calocitta troglodytes</i>	PE	X			X
Columbidae	<i>Phapitreron leucotis</i>	PE				X
	<i>Chalcophaps indica</i>	R				X
Corvidae	<i>Corvus macrorhynchos</i>	R	X			
Cuculidae	<i>Centropus bengalensis</i>	R	X	X		
	<i>Centropus viridis</i>	PE	X			
Dicaeidae	<i>Dicaeum trigonostigma</i>	R		X		
	<i>Dicaeum australe</i>	PE		X	X	
Estrildidae	<i>Lonchura leucogastra</i>	R		X	X	X
	<i>Lonchura malacca</i>	R		X		X
Hemiprocnidae	<i>Hemiprocne comata</i>	R		X	X	
Hirundinidae	<i>Hirundo tahitica</i>	R		X		
Laniidae	<i>Lanius cristatus</i>	M	X	X		
Meropidae	<i>Merops viridis</i>	R				X
Motacillidae	<i>Motacilla flava</i>	M	X	X		
	<i>Nectarinia jugularis</i>	R	X	X	X	X
Nectariniidae	<i>Nectarinia sperata</i>	R	X			
	<i>Bolbo psittacus lunulatus</i>	PE				X
Pycnonotidae	<i>Pycnonotus goiavier</i>	R	X	X	X	X
Strigidae	<i>Otus mirus</i>	ME	X			X
Sturnidae	<i>Aplonis minor</i>	PE	X	X	X	
	<i>Aplonis panayensis</i>	R	X	X		
	Total		13	13	6	11
	Percentage		30.23	30.23	13.95	25.58
	No. of Phil. endemic		4	2	2	4
	No. of Min. endemic		1	0	0	1

Legend: PE-Philippine endemic, R-Resident, M-Migrant; ME-Mindanao Endemic.

One of the most important data in the study is the discovery of *Alcedo argentata* (Silvery Kingfisher) which is assessed as 'Vulnerable' by IUCN Red List of Threatened Species (IUCN Red List of Threatened Species, 2016-1). This species is only found in the remaining forest fragment at Sitio Tindalo, one of the remaining relatively undisturbed areas in MHSPL.

Table 2 shows that Sitio New Bohol and Sitio Saraban has the highest number of species richness with 13 species (30.23%), followed by Sitio Tindalo with 11 species (25.58%) and Sitio Pagtulian with 6 species (13.95%). However based on endemism, Sitio New Bohol and Sitio Tindalo has the highest number of Philippine endemic species. The following Philippine endemic species are: *Accipiter virgatus*, *Alcedo argentata*, *Callocalia troglodytes*, *Phapitreron leucotis*, *Centropus viridis*, *Dicaeum australe*, *Bolbo psittacus lunulatus*, and *Aplonis minor*. The only Mindanao endemic species recorded is *Otus mirus* (Mindanao Scops Owl) found only in Sitio Tindalo and New Bohol.

The relatively high number of endemic species in Sitio New Bohol and Sitio Tindalo compared to Sitio Saraban and Sitio Pagtulian is the presence of fragmented forests which serve as habitat and source of food is still available in these areas. Sitio New Bohol although started to be mined by the local villagers, still small forest cover can be seen in the area. Sitio Tindalo is the remaining area in MHSPL where secondary forests thrive which we presumed the last haven of endemic bird species in MHSPL. Hence immediate conservation efforts especially forest protection to these areas, Sitio New Bohol and Sitio Tindalo is urgently needed.

Conclusion

Despite the rampant mining and other socio-economic activities inside the MHSPL there is still good number of avifaunal species surviving in its remaining forests. This is evident in the presence of some Philippine and Mindanao endemic species including the *Otus mirus* (Mindanao Scops Owl) and the rare and vulnerable *Alcedo argentata* (Silvery Kingfisher) found only in Sitio Tindalo.

Therefore, an urgent forest protection should be implemented especially in Sitio New Bohol and Sitio Tindalo where majority of endemic species are found.

Acknowledgement

Our gratitude to the Research Development Centre of Assumption College of Nabunturan for the funding during fieldwork; Balik-Kinaiyahan Foundation Incorporated headed by Dr. Wenifredo Maglana for the funds, technical, and logistic support; Biology students of Assumption College of Nabunturan; Raffy Paig, Kim Jumawan, Niño Ben Salarda, Analie Gone, Willen Joy Domingo, Cherry Piones; Nannel Aranton, John Marco Suazo, Neil Balbon, Dr. Patria Painaga, Sr. Rhassy Love Tiongson, fma.; Field guides, Tata, Jojo, and Tatay; Barangay council of Bukal and Mainit; Lastly to the late Sir Fred Trangia and company for the food and security of the team.

References

- Broad G, Oliveros C.** 2004. Biodiversity and conservation priority setting in the Babuyan Islands, Philippines. *Technical Journal of Philippine Ecosystems and Natural Resources* **15**, 1-30.
- Brooks TM, Pimm SL, Collar NJ.** 1997. Deforestation predicts the number of threatened birds in Insular Southeast Asia. *Conservation Biology* **11(2)**, 382-394.
- Brooks TM, Pimm SL, Kapos V, Ravilious C.** 1999. Threat from deforestation to montane and lowland birds and mammals in insular South-east Asia. *Journal of Animal Ecology* **68**, 1061-1078.
- Bueser GL, Bueser KG, Afan DS, Salvador DI, Grier JW, Kennedy RS, Miranda HC Jr.** 2003. Distribution and nesting density of the Philippine Eagle *Pithecophaga jefferyi* on Mindanao Island, Philippines: What do we know after 100 years?. *British Ornithologist Union, Ibis* **145**, 130-135.
- Clout MN, Hay JR.** 1989. The importance of birds as browsers, pollinators and seed dispersers in New Zealand forest. *New Zealand Journal of Ecology* **12**, 27-33.

- Collar NJ, Mallari NA, Tabaranza BR.** 1999. Threatened birds of the Philippines. Manila, Philippines: Bookmark.
- Conservation International - Biodiversity Hotspots.** 2007. Conservation International. Retrieved December 5, 2011 from <http://www.biodiversityhotspots.org>.
- Conservation International-Philippines.** 2006. Priority Sites for Conservation in the Philippines: Key Biodiversity Areas. Department of Environment and Natural Resources-Protected Areas and Wildlife Bureau and Haribon Foundation. Quezon City Philippines.
- Derlindanti EJ, Caziani SM.** 2005. Using Canopy and Understory Mist Nets and Point Counts to Study Bird Assemblages in Chaco Forest. *Wilson Bulletin* **17(6)**, 92-99.
- Featured protected area: Mainit Hotpring Protected Landscape.** 2009. Philippine Clearing House Mechanism for Biodiversity. Retrieved November 25, 2011. from www.chm.ph/index.
- Fujita MS, Tuttle MD.** 1991. Flying foxes (Chiroptera: Pteropodidae): Threatened animals of key ecological and economic importance. *Conservation Biology* **5(4)**, 455-463.
- Gonzalez JCT, Ajuang LE, Dans ATL.** 1995. A Manual in Wildlife 101 Introduction to Philippine Wildlife. Wildlife Biology Laboratory, Institute of Biological Sciences, College of Arts and Sciences, University of the Philippines at Los Baños, Philippines.
- Heaney LR, Balete DS, Dolar L, Alcalá AC, Dans PC, Gonzales N, Ingle N, Lepiten W, Oliver EA, Rickart BR, Tabaranza Jr, Uzzurum RC.** 1998. A synopsis of the mammalian fauna of the Philippine Islands. *Fieldiana Zoology new series* **88**, 1-61.
- Heaney LR, Regalado JC.** 1998. Vanishing treasures of the Philippine rain forest. Chicago: The Field Museum.
- IUCN Red List of Threatened Species.** 2011. International Union for Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources. Retrieved February 20, 2012. from www.iucnredlist.org
- Kennedy RS, Gonzales PC, Dickinson EC, Miranda HC Jr, Fisher TH.** 2000. A guide to the birds of the Philippines. London: Oxford University Press.
- Mickleburgh SP, Hutson AM, Racey PA.** 1992. Old World Fruit Bats: An action plan for their conservation. IUCN/SSC Chiroptera Specialist Group IUCN, Gland, Switzerland.
- Mittermeier R, Gil PR, Hoffman M, Pilgrim J, Brooks T, Mittermeier CG, Lamoreux J, de Fonseca GAB.** 2005. Hotspots Revisited: Earth's Biologically Richest and Most Threatened Ecoregions. Conservation International, Virginia USA.
- O'Malley R, King T, Turner CS, Tyler S, Benares J, Cummings M, Raines P.** 2006. The diversity and distribution of the fruit bat fauna (Mammalia, Chiroptera, Megachiroptera) of Danjungan Island, Cauayan, Negros Occidental, Philippines (with notes on the *Microchiroptera*). *Biodiversity and Conservation* **15**, 43-56.
- Olofsson J, Hulme PE, Oksanen L, Suominen O.** 2004. Importance of large and small mammalian herbivores for the plant community structure in the forest tundra ecotone. *OIKOS* **106**, 324-334.
- Peterson AT.** 2006. Taxonomy is important in conservation: a preliminary reassessment of Philippine species-level bird taxonomy. *Bird Conservation International* **16**, 155-173.
- Pimm SL, Russell GJ, Gittleman JL, Brooks TM.** 1995. The future of biodiversity. *Science* **269**, 347-350.
- Relox RE, Leaño EP, Camino FA.** 2009. Elevational Gradation Of Mammals in Tropical Forest of Mt. Hamiguitan Range, Davao Oriental, *Journal of nature Studies* **8(1)**, 27-34.

- Relox RE, Leño EP, Camino FA.** 2011. Avifaunal assemblage in Mt. Hamiguitan, Davao Oriental, Mindanao Island, Philippines. *Journal of Environmental Science and Management* **14(1)**, 1-11.
- Relox RE, Leño EP, Camino FA.** 2011. Herpetofaunal Endemism and Diversity in Tropical Forest of Mt. Hamiguitan in the Philippines. *Herpetological Conservation and Biology* **6(1)**, 107-113.
- Stuart AM, Prescott CV, Singleton GR.** 2011. Is a native rodent competitively dominant over an invasive rodent in lowland agro-forest habitat of the Philippines? *Julius-Kühn-Archiv*, **432**, 167-168.
- Suarez RK, Sajise PE.** 2010. Deforestation, swidden agriculture and Philippine biodiversity. *Philippine Science Letters* **3(1)**, 91-99.
- Tamblyn A, Turner C, Turner A, Raines P.** 2005. A Comparative Study of the habitats of the upper Imbang-Caliban watershed, North Negros forest reserve, Negros Occidental Philippines. *The Negros Rainforest Conservation* 1-72.
- The Field Museum.** 2010. Synopsis of Philippine Mammals. Retrieved February 15, 2012 from www.archive.fieldmuseum.org/philippine_mammals
- Turner A, Sanderson E, Sweet M, Raines P.** 2006. The Biodiversity of the lower-montane forest habitats of the North Negros forest reserve, Negros Occidental, Philippines. *The Negros Rainforest Conservation* 1-58.